

The Ideas of Intellectual Activity, Knowledge, Information and Data applicable in the Knowledge Management, Artificial Intelligence and Intellect Modeling

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Abstract. This paper focuses on a new concept of intellectual activity, knowledge, Information and data that applicable in the Knowledge Management, Artificial Intelligence and Intellect Modeling. These terms are not well defined, and because of that software developers are not sure what they are doing. The terms proposed are clear and understandable by any interested person. They are used extensively in the Intellect Modeling. The paper includes also discussion of the following questions. Is there any general direction in a progress of cybernetics and information technologies or it consists of many independent movements? What needs are served by IT? What approaches are used by IT products? Where IT going?

Keywords: Knowledge management, Information technology, Artificial intelligence, Intellect modeling, Philosophy.

1 Introduction

"We are drowning in information but starved for knowledge" (John Naisbitt, author of Megatrend).

If you have no problems—simply enjoy your life! You need no any papers on intellectual activity, knowledge, data, and so on. This rather complex paper is intended for those who have problems, want to solve them and don't know how. It is also can be helpful for those which business is to help others to solve their problems and find opportunities.

2 Methods, Results and Discussion

This section provides the general methodologies used. The aim is to provide enough details for other researchers to fully replicate results. It is also facilitate better understanding of the results obtained.

This section also focuses on the results of the research performed and discussion.

2.1 An attempt to present ideas of terms in the paper

1. Data

It is everything that could be perceived by a man: text, sound, pictures, multimedia. We believe that the main task on which Information Technologies (IT) now oriented is data management. All kinds of hardware and software are well suited for data capturing and distribution. But who needs this data? If it is collected regardless of people using it – it is senseless. Ordinary users don't need data as it is and can not do such a high skill demanding work as data mining.

2. Information

That part of data, which is directly connected to the knowledge possessed by a perceiving man. It is obvious that this part is variable depending on the experience of persons.

Usually what users are expecting from IT is to get an information helping them to solve their problems. For example, if you want to fly by plane, you should like to get flights schedule. But data that you will get from computers became an information only in that case when it is relevant to your experience, to your own knowledge. If you don't know what is an airplane – flights schedule will be useless for you. Therefore the main difficulty for users is how to find data that will become an information. That's why search and categorization systems are extremely important part of IT. For users it is not very interesting where needed data resides - in databases, document management systems, HTML files etc. They will prefer to have only one data access point to all sources, including human experts. We see from quotations above that understanding of this fact leads many companies to the implementation of Knowledge Management (KM) systems. But it is rather complicated task to find information with search engines based on the morphological retrieval indexes

and not on ideas searching. Try Internet search engines, for example, to find definition of airplane if you don't know what is it. Categorization is easier to use, but it is too rigid and relatively poor for a good description of data sources.

3. Explicit knowledge (external)

From our point of view this is constant and the most valuable part of data source, not depending on any person. And it is the part that we are learning on.

We already have proposed to define knowledge elements as 3-parts stable memory patterns.

1. *Description of a problem*
2. *Name of a problem*
3. *Description of a problem solution*

There is 1st level knowledge – concrete, which was developed during concrete problems solving, and 2nd level knowledge - abstract, which was developed on the basis of concrete knowledge. It is typical situations and solutions, general rules etc.

4. Individual knowledge (tacit)

Types of tacit knowledge include hands-on skills, special know-how, intuitions, and the like. Michael Polanyi, the first to distinguish tacit from explicit knowledge, stated "We can know more than we can tell."

Sure, almost any kind of knowledge is initially tacit. All intellectual activity of person goes in sub-consciousness, and therefore does not need words. Words appear at a level of consciousness (co-knowledge), which is many times poorer than sub-consciousness.

2.2 What is intellectual activity?

As we know, the main tool, which humans use to survive, is an intellect. Without intellect all other tools are useless and even can do harm instead of good. Let's try to understand what is intellectual activity of a man and how to make it fruitful.

"He possesses two out of the three qualities necessary for the ideal detective. He has the power of observation and that of deduction. He is only wanting in knowledge, and that may come in time." (Mr Sherlock Holmes, THE SIGN OF FOUR, p.91) [1]

We would like to mention that Sherlock Holmes stories were written by Sir Arthur Conan Doyle to illustrate methods of the intellectual activity of brilliant experts like Dr. Joseph Bell of the Edinburgh Infirmary (see preface of Christopher Morley). Sir Arthur Conan Doyle was known expert too. Therefore we believe that he described the intellectual activity in a right way.

Following Mr Sherlock Holmes, we can find following steps of intellectual activity:

1. *Observation - getting data and information*
2. *Producing propositions, based on the knowledge*
3. *Selection and verification of the most appropriate propositions*
4. *Memorizing - converting data to information and new knowledge item creation*
5. *Abstraction finding – building artificial objects representing group of real objects, featuring typical signs of group*

1st step. Observation

The first step is collection of data and information. Without it all other steps are senseless. We propose to treat as 'data' everything that could be perceived by a man: text, sound, pictures, multimedia etc. And part of data, which is directly connected to the knowledge possessed by a man, we propose to call 'information'. It is the part that is really involved in a problems solving. For example, imagine that you are listening to a very interesting lecture and speaker is using sometimes a language that you don't understand. Then that part of the lecture in a foreign language is simply 'data' for you just like music. And part of the lecture in a local language may contain valuable information helping you. It is

obvious that this part is variable depending on the experience of the person - what is valuable for one person, may be useless for other.

2nd step. Producing propositions based on the knowledge

Knowledge is a simplified model of certain human intellect which can assist to answer questions like "What is it and how it is called?" and "What we should do in a present situation?" Elementary items of knowledge have form of "If Situation Then Action" rules sometimes called productions as introduced by famous experts in Artificial Intelligence Alan Newell and Herbert Simon - developers of General Problem Solver.

Taking into account this definition, we propose to define knowledge elements as 3-parts stable memory patterns. Each pattern contains:

1. *Description of a problem - data, memorized at the time of a problem solving*
2. *Name of a problem - should be unique text*
3. *Description of a problem solution - the actions needed for a solution verification and application, expected result*

How to describe a problem and its solution?

People, as a rule, use words to describe their problems. There are so many words, and number of their combinations is countless. It may seem impossible to find a sense in a such huge amount of data. But, fortunately, what is really important - it's ideas. Plenty of words are just like clothes that people wear. The same man can wear different garment and remain unchanged as a personality. Therefore we believe that description may be transformed into a set of standard ideas. We propose to define "idea's text" as a standard text unequivocally defining a specific side of a situation i.e. representing a stable structure in a brain's right part responsible for images of the world. We think that intellectual activity is based on ideas as images of the world, but not on specific words representing them. This text should not include any excessive words and the words included should always have the right sense. For example, people may say: "It looks so green to me"; "I think it's a greenish stuff"; "It reminds me a fresh grass." The idea's text should be: "The color is green." Note that people can express the same idea with words absolutely different.

And what the number of such ideas could be?

Famous American psychologist Mr Cattell in his work "Universal Index of Source Traits" [2] has made an attempt to propose a list of items for a human personality features description. Preliminary list included 4,550 different items used by many authors. After excluding synonyms it was appeared that only 171 were left [3]. The same result we have got from our experience (medicine, art, banking, business etc). Number of ideas used for a description of problems and their solutions in a particular area of knowledge, which may be learned by one man, was always not exceeded several hundreds. It seems that this limitation of ideas number might be the individual human brain restraint. Take into account that human brain is a multi-floor building and what we see is only upper floor. Though we think that there should exist areas which are complex by the nature. For example, total list of possible diseases of World Health Organization exceeds several tens thousand items – absolutely beyond possibilities of any expert.

We should note that only humans have the ability to define ideas and to exclude synonyms. It is highly creative intellectual activity.

An expert produces propositions based on his own knowledge:

"As a rule, when I have heard some slight indication of the course of events, I am able to guide myself by the thousands of other similar cases which occur to my memory." (Mr Sherlock Holmes, THE READ-HEADED LEAGUE, p.176) [1]

3rd step. Selection and verification of the most appropriate propositions

"...you now pretend to deduce this knowledge I could only say what was the balance of probability. I did not at all expect to be so accurate." (Mr Sherlock Holmes, THE SIGN OF FOUR, p.93) [1]

"For example, observation shows me that you have been to the Wigmore Street Post-Office this morning, but deduction lets me know that when there you dispatched a telegram... The rest is deduction...Why, of course I knew that you had not written a letter, since I sat opposite to you all morning. I see also in your open desk that you have a sheet of

stamps and a thick bundle of postcards. What could you go into the post-office for, then, but to send a wire ? Eliminate all other factors, and the one which remains must be the truth." (Mr Sherlock Holmes, THE SIGN OF FOUR, p.91) [1]

4th step. Memorizing - converting data to information and new knowledge item creation

If the problem was solved - proven success or proven fail, then there should appear a new memory element including problem's description, problem's name and description of problem's solution. Data is transforming into information and any new problem with similar description will cause possible solution proposition appearing based on this knowledge element.

5th step. Abstraction finding – building artificial objects representing group of real objects, featuring typical signs of group

Abstraction analysis is intended to find groups of similar objects and regularities they are based on. The central point is an ability of human brain to find similar objects descriptions inside memory. The brain can do it almost instantly.

3 Discussion

Any kind of data will be useless if a man has very little own knowledge. Therefore people need to learn to work effectively. And in many cases IT can help. For example, you can use distance learning... But evidently it is very time-consuming activity and, therefore, amount of knowledge learned is small comparatively to all existing knowledge.

There is great amount of applicable knowledge in the world. Before using a man should learn it. To learn it is the task far beyond possibilities of any man. We are becoming richer in knowledge but can not use our treasures. Oddly enough?

3.1 Learning

Exams:

Prof.: You are looking very worried. Any problems with exams questions?

Stud.: Oh, no! Questions are OK. It is the answers that I worry about.

Knowledge is working only when it is inside human brain. Learning information about knowledge contained in manuals does not mean possessing knowledge. The difference between educated human graduated from high school and experienced human is the following. Educated human has read about knowledge but has no experience to apply it and therefore has no actions memory involved. Actions memory is located as a rule in the left half of brain as opposite to environment memory located as a rule in the right half of brain. Experienced human has this actions memory filled and in a case of familiar needs and environment combination should automatically propose possible solutions from the actions memory.

3.2 Traditional Learning

Traditional learning is based on linear process, when students must learn all proposed knowledge, topic by topic. Then, students must pass exams to get acknowledgement from professors that knowledge is in their minds. Initial time of learning is great. There are many exams, sometimes very difficult, having great influence on the life of students. But all this hard work does not guarantee that students have all or even greater part of knowledge needed to solve problems, which arise in their post-school activity, in a real world life.

3.3 Adaptive Learning

Is adaptive learning new in principle?

It seems that adaptive learning is the main stream of human life-long learning activity, though usually we are not trying to distinguish directly traditional learning from adaptive. Traditional learning supplies us with preliminary education, knowledge of language needed to learn further, and with great amount of knowledge "just-in-case". After that, during all our life, we are trying to find and learn knowledge needed to solve our problems in a working activity. We are learning not in a formal manner in special institutions but as a rule, by our own efforts. And it should be called adaptive learning.

"Just-in-time" knowledge

Adaptive learning tools, such as e-knowledge systems, are based on a concept called Just-in-time knowledge (JIT-Knowledge). The volume of knowledge is great. No one can learn it all. But, fortunately, in real activity we need only knowledge applied to existing problems. Thus this knowledge should be called Just-In-Time Knowledge.

Why adaptive learning tools are not widely recognized?

Till now adaptive learning was mainly manual activity, very time- and efforts-consuming. If we have a real problem, but don't know - how to solve it, whether solution exists and where to learn it, we are trying to find a person experienced in that kind of problems - expert, professor, doctor. And this person can tell us how to find facilities to learn how to solve a problem. But it is hard work to find right expert and in many cases we can appeal to a person not experienced in these problems, and get wrong advice.

For example, medical diagnostics is a very complicated matter. If we are trying to get medical advice from a person not experienced in area of real patient's problem (it may occur, because list of World Health Organization counts thousands possible diseases), we are at risk to get wrong diagnosis and treatment. It is common problem in many countries, including developed. Practically all medical institutions resist attempts to disclose their medical errors statistics.

3.4 Cybernetics

Cybernetics studies control and communications in living beings and machines. The main question is whether it is possible to create thinking machines? Information Science, Information Technologies, Informatics and Computing frequently are considered as branches of cybernetics. [4]

3.5 Information Technologies

The further development of "data processing" lead to "information systems", "data-base management systems", "information technologies", "information retrieval systems", "search engines", "directories". The main point is an attempt to assist human persons in data storing and searching for information relevant both their experience and problems appeared. Main principles are using keywords and taxonomy (hierarchy) to find needed information. The known example is Internet search engines and directories like Google, Yahoo, DuckDuckGo etc.

Text Mining Technologies recently have appeared to support summarization, feature extraction, clustering, classification, question answering, thematic indexing and keyword searching in a huge amount of text files. The products developed are Intelligent Miner for Text by IBM, TextAnalyst by Megaputer, Text Miner by SAS Institute, Semiomap by Entrieva, Oracle Text by Oracle, Autonomy Knowledge Server by Autonomy etc. This technology as we see should accompany search engines and directories providing automatic preliminary processing of millions of text documents.

IT tools proposed should be estimated as not strong enough, providing two types of faults: you will get data you don't need, and you will not get information you really need. The first is irritating, and the second is very disappointing indeed - information exists, but you may not use it. Computers in principle are well suited for capturing, processing and dissemination of various data types. Initial title of computing was "data processing". First computers were used primarily for complex mathematics calculations, but not for data storage and handling. With the time many types of data input and output devices as well as data memory were created for computers that has lead the way to information technologies.

Evidently many products were developed to support pure data processing like mathematics applications, office packages, CAD systems, players etc.

3.6 Artificial Intelligence

The main goal of Artificial Intelligence was an attempt to build intelligence not based on human knowledge [5],[6],[7].

For over 80 years there were many attempts to replace human experts. The most popular in this branch of research known as Artificial Intelligence are computer programs called expert systems and devices called neural networks. An expert system is an example of a 'top-down' approach when particular instances of intelligent behavior selected and an

attempt to design machines that can replicate that behavior was made. A neural network is an example of 'bottom-up' approach when there is an attempt to study the biological mechanisms that underlie human intelligence and to build machines, which work on similar principles.

OpenAI CEO Sam Altman says AI like LLM ChatGPT will reshape society, acknowledges risks: 'A little bit scared of this. "I'm particularly worried that these models could be used for large-scale disinformation," Altman said. "Now that they're getting better at writing computer code, [they] could be used for offensive cyberattacks." But a consistent issue with AI language models like ChatGPT, according to Altman, is misinformation: The program can give users factually inaccurate information. "Altman said relying on the system as a primary source of accurate information "is something you should not use it for," and encourages users to double-check the program's results." [8]

Eunika Mercier-Laurent state in a paper *The Future of AI or AI for the Future* "The third hype of AI and enthusiasm for applying last techniques in all fields raise great interest and some important questions on the future directions in AI research and applications. Guiding by the principle of combing the best from human and computers capacities this chapter lists some important challenges to face and related directions in AI research"[9].

3.7 General Knowledge Machine

Environment => Meaningful Perception => Information

As a rule people don't memorize environment information itself since it rarely should be applied readily. Information technologies such as databases and search engines are devoted primarily to information storing and retrieval. They do no distinction between information and knowledge treating all sources as sources of information.

Situation (Needs+Environment) => Solution (Actions) => Knowledge

We believe that knowledge is the only solid ground to act wisely. Environment information is one part needed, but there are other parts: needs description supplied by people and solution description memorized by people in the existing knowledge.

General Knowledge Machine Research Group introduced Electronic Knowledge Publishing based on the General Knowledge Machine technology with the aim to provide efficient tools for any kind of knowledge-based applications, supporting effective knowledge presentation, precise knowledge search, adaptive learning and immediate consulting. [10] [11]

GKM technology supplies with ability to build e-knowledge systems as tools supporting JIT-knowledge implementation due to simulation of human-like environment and actions memories activity. This gives a possibility to find and to learn only knowledge needed in a particular situation.

Since this approach doesn't bind to any specific area of knowledge but to human intellect activity, there are no limitations on application. Every knowledge-consuming application may be supported with GKM technology. Our own implementations were in medicine, banking, psychology, business, and arts. We could propose, for example, organization knowledge warehouse development, much more effective in knowledge handling than conventional warehouses and so on.

3.8 Knowledge Management

There are many attempts to define it.

Knowledge management (KM) is the process of creating, sharing, using and managing the knowledge and information of an organization.

One part is connected with general assets management theory. If you have assets, you should manage them, have warehouses for them etc. It results in development of super-database, containing all possible kinds of data sources, with super-search and retrieval engine accessed with universal type of client software, mostly Internet browser. These tools are intended for knowledge consumers.

The other part is connected with knowledge ecology, virtual team development, communities of practice, providing knowledge exteriorization and possibilities for learning. This part is for knowledge producers.

We think that there should be part having the goal to pass significant part of intellectual work to machines. Why? Ability of a person to learn and therefore to apply knowledge is limited - remember school, university etc. Amount of knowledge is becoming greater, but who will learn and apply it? Intranet/Internet and emerging e-knowledge systems methodology may allow all people to learn in an adaptive way and to use great knowledge immediately. We think that advantages are obvious, that's why General Knowledge Machine Research Group is developing e-knowledge publishing. It is working; you may evaluate it at <https://gkm-ekp.sf.net>

4 Conclusion and Perspectives

Today many organizations treat knowledge as their most valuable asset. Information technologies and training programs are considered as not enough to support knowledge development and application effectively. That's why such movements as knowledge management and knowledge innovation appear to find new possibilities in intellectual activities management.

General Knowledge Machine Research Group proposes innovative but absolutely practical and reliable approach for organization's knowledge storing and dissemination. There exists already significant experience developing e-knowledge systems in various areas including medicine, arts, management, banking and psychology.

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6 Declarations Introduction

5.1. Ethics Approval

Not applicable

5.2. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

5.3. Data Availability

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

5.4. Author Contribution

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5.6. Consent to publish

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